

**A MODERN POWERFUL ARMY IS A GUARANTEE OF OUR LIFE IN
PEACE**

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Annotation: *It reflects the reforms of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021.*

Keyword: *To increase the strength of our Armed Forces, to resolutely pursue the path of national development and raise it to a new level, to further improve the organizational system of the Armed Forces, to train its personnel, to set specific tasks for its further development, to train military personnel.*

Each State has its own administrative boundaries. Our brave soldiers are guarding the sacred frontier day and night, day and night, conscientiously, risking their lives if necessary, despite the bitter cold and heat. Many reforms have been implemented in 2017-2021 for these honorable professionals. President ShavkatMirziyoyevMiramonovich in his book "We will resolutely pursue the path of national development and raise it to a new level" ... requires the mobilization of all our migration and capabilities. That is why, like other spheres of social and political life of the country, the urgent tasks in this direction are clearly defined in the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, which is currently being developed.

According to this important document, measures will be taken to increase the effectiveness of the legislative framework in the field of defense, the combat composition, organizational structure, training and recruitment of military personnel. In addition, specific measures have been taken and will be taken to improve the armament of the armed forces with modern weapons and equipment and their comprehensive provision.

Dear and respected President!

On this auspicious occasion, I would like to express our sincere gratitude to our brave sons - soldiers and officers, all the guardians of the Motherland, and their parents, who are fulfilling their responsible and honorable duty in the military.

Congratulations from the President!

From the bottom of my heart, I once again congratulate you, dear people, in your person, on the 25th anniversary of the establishment of our Armed Forces. Words of the President! Modern, powerful The army is a guarantee of our peaceful life.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces ShavkatMirziyoyev On January 26, 2017, a meeting was held with the leadership of

the Ministry of Defense at the Tashkent Higher Military Command School. Members of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan took part in the event.

The head of our state set specific tasks aimed at increasing the effectiveness of legislation in the field of security, further improving the organizational system of the Armed Forces, training its personnel.

Issues related to the comprehensive social protection of servicemen, including the construction of modern housing for servicemen and their families were discussed. President ShavkatMirziyoyevMiramonovich pays special attention to such important tasks as educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, raising the sense of responsibility of our compatriots for the fate and future of the Motherland.

At the meeting, members of the government, heads of ministries and departments were instructed to further improve the work on strengthening the capacity of our Armed Forces. specific instructions were given to further strengthen the unity of our national army and people.

The head of state got acquainted with the conditions created for cadets at the university on January 26, 2017

This is what the book of our President ShavkatMirziyoyevMiramonovich, "The consent of our people is the highest value given to our activities," said. It was held on the eve of the 26th anniversary of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Defender of the

Fatherland Day. Exactly a year ago, at the Academy of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miramonovich discussed in detail the tasks ahead of us to further reform the Armed Forces of our country. At the meeting of Shavkat Mirziyoev Miramonovich, the issue of improving the activities of the Academy was considered as one of the urgent tasks in the field of military training. ShavkatMirziyoyevMiramonovich analyzed the combat readiness and capabilities of the Armed Forces during the year.

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